

AI-PRISM

Launch of the AI-PRISM Open-Access Alliance: a stakeholder ecosystem to foster new AI-driven smart manufacturing solutions.

September 2024

Press Release

The [AI-PRISM project](#), funded by Horizon Europe, aims to revolutionize manufacturing processes with human-centered AI solutions that boost customer satisfaction and productivity. It focuses on collaborative robotics adaptable for smaller productions in SMEs, enhancing robot-human cooperation with intuitive programming for real-time interactions. The project also integrates social sciences to ensure robots maintain not just physical, but psychological safety for workers, considering factors like gender and sociocultural differences.

The [AI-PRISM Open-Access Alliance](#) is set to harness the technical solutions and pilot cases developed within the AI-PRISM project, aiming to broaden access to the results and build a robust ecosystem of stakeholders. This initiative ensures the reuse of these outcomes across various scenarios, fostering the development of new human-centric AI-powered smart manufacturing solutions, as well as creating new business opportunities.

This Alliance includes a diverse range of stakeholders, such as **solution developers, product engineers, system administrators, operators, infrastructure providers, and end-users, including SMEs and companies across the EU.**

Joining the alliance provides opportunities for **resource capitalization, accelerated upskilling, early experimentation, risk-free testing, and access to training and certifications.**

The AI-PRISM project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101058589.

Access and Membership

Access to the Open-Access platform is provided through the **AI-PRISM Open-Access Network Portal**, offering a wide array of AI tools, industrial equipment, and robotic systems.

Members can experiment with new technologies, develop innovative applications, and share data and knowledge.

To join the **AI-PRISM Open-Access Alliance** and receive more information about membership, send an e-mail to openaccess@aiprism.eu

Contact us!

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Learn more about AI-PRISM at

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